

SEMANTIC FEATURES OF NEGATIVE PRONOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the specifics of negative pronouns in English and Uzbek. The bilingual meanings of negative pronouns, their use in speech, and their meanings in translation have been studied comparatively. In addition, the structural position of the negative pronouns in the sentence was also analyzed in both Uzbek and English languages.*

Key words: *Negative Pronouns, no, none, nobody, never, no one, neither, either, nothing, nowhere, nothing, all, everybody, every, each Interrogative pronoun, [double negation](#)*

Introduction

In recent years, a special focus on science and education has placed researchers in positions of responsibility in both theoretical and practical fields. One such task is to learn and teach foreign languages. Significant work is being done in our country to develop the study of foreign languages.

As an example, to create conditions for the development of students' basic language skills (listening, reading, writing and speaking), including the organization of in-depth study of foreign languages by merging foreign language departments of higher education institutions; introduction of internationally recognized methods of teaching students in foreign languages and assessment of their knowledge, including the widespread use of distance and other modern forms of education in the educational process, as well as the teaching of other subjects in foreign languages; ensuring that students' mastery of at least two foreign languages broadens their horizons, increases their potential, and increases their competitiveness in the labor market [1].

There are many different and similar aspects of negative pronouns in English and Uzbek. In this article, we want to analyze the semantic features of negative pronouns in English and Uzbek.

Methodology

The negative pronouns no, none, nobody, no one, nothing, neither are closely connected with the indefinite and defining pronouns. Most of the indefinite

pronouns correlate with the negative pronouns: some – no, none, something – nothing, none, somebody, someone, one – nobody, no one, none [3].

Some defining pronouns are the opposites of the negative pronouns: everything – nothing, all, everybody, every, each – no, none, nobody, both, either – neither.

No is used only before a noun as an adjective-substitute in the function of attribute: There is no telephone in our house. He is no gentleman.

None is used as a noun-substitute and takes a singular verb: I'm afraid we can't have coffee – there's none left. When none is followed by of it may take either a singular or plural verb: There are faults from which none of us is/are free. None of them has/have come back yet. In the sentence none is either subject or object. For example: None of this money is mine, (subject) They chose none but the best, (object)

The negative pronouns nobody and no-one are noun-substitutes and refer to human beings only. They correlate with somebody, someone and all, every, each and everybody. They are mostly used as subjects and objects: Nobody could find their luggage. No-one likes to be criticized, (subject) We saw nobody we knew, (object) [5].

Nothing is a noun-substitute that refers to things. It is opposed to something and everything. In the sentence it is used as subject, predicative and object. For example: Nothing I could say had any influence on her. (subject) He's had nothing to eat yet. (object) She's nothing to me. (predicative)

The negative pronoun neither is the opposite of either and both. It can be used as both a noun- and adjective-substitute. As a noun-substitute it is used with of before a plural noun and takes a singular verb: Neither of the statements is true.

In the sentence neither of functions as subject and object: Neither of them was happy, (subject) / like neither of them, (object)

As an adjective-substitute neither takes a singular noun, functioning as an attribute: Neither neither statement is true. I can agree in neither case [4].

In Uzbek, pronouns are words that substitute for nouns or adjectives. The negative pronouns *hech kim*, *hech nima*, *hech kimga*, *hech nimaga*, *hech qanday*, *hech qancha*, *hech qayer* are used to talk about absent or nonexistent things and people.

Consider these examples:

Uyda hech narsa yo'q.

(There is nothing at home.)

U hech kimni tanimaydi.

(He doesn't know anybody.)

The negative pronouns are formed from the interrogative pronouns with the help of such prefix as *hech* and affix *-ma*. For example [2]:

Interrogative pronoun	Negative pronoun
kim	Hech kim
qancha	Hech qancha
nima	Hech nima
qachon	Hech qachon

Note that *hech-* is always stressed. It is used to negate. On the contrary, the prefix *ma-* is never stressed. It is used to intensify negation. Here are some examples:

Men **hech** nima qilmadim. *hech-* is used to intensify the negation formed by the verb *qilmadim* and the particle *hech*.
 I was doing nothing.

Mening **hech** qanday ishim yo'q. *hech-* is used to show that an action can not be performed because there is no an object (i.e. there is nothing to do)
 I have nothing to do.

Discussion and results

Nowadays, We are learning a whole bunch of Uzbek and English pronouns: personal, demonstrative, possessive, determinative and reflexive ones. There is one more group of Uzbek and English pronouns that we have not covered yet, it is called negative pronouns. So in this article, we will discuss what they are and how to use them in both languages.

The same way as in English you have such negative pronouns as *nobody, none, nothing, never, nowhere*, etc., there are equivalents of them in Uzbek.

They are:

- *hech kim - nobody*
- *hech nima - nothing*
- *hech qaysi - none*
- *hech qanday - by no means, not at all, in no way, nowise*
- *hech kimniki - nobody's, no one's*
- *hech qancha - none at all*
- *hech qachon - never*
- *hech qayerda - nowhere (location)*
- *hech qayerga - nowhere (direction)*

- hech qayerdan – *from nowhere e.c.t.*

As you can see, all of them are formed by simply adding the prefix **hech-** to the pronouns that you already know. Let's have a look at how and when you can use them:

-**hech** kim menga yordam bera ol**may**di

- *No one can help me.*

- **Hech** narsa o'tkazib yuboril**may**di.

- *Nothing is missing.*

- Qanday sumka senga ko'proq yoqadi? - **Hech** qanday.

- *Which backpack do you like more? - None.*

- Men senga **hech** qanday yordam bera ol**may**man.

- *I can't help you in any way.*

- Bu kimning to'pi? - **Hech** kimning.

- *Whose ball is this? - Nobody's.*

- Men sizga umuman shubha qil**may**man.

- *I have no doubt in you.*

- **Hech** qachon **hech** qachon dema.

- *Never say never.*

- Menga kerakli narsani **hech** qayerdan topa ol**may**apman.

- *I cannot find what I need anywhere.*

As you have noticed, all the negative sentences above have both a negative pronoun and **-ma**, which is unusual for English. It is because [double negation](#) is a norm in Uzbek.

Negative pronouns with prepositions

Pay attention, that used with prepositions, negative pronouns separate in two parts (prefix and the base pronoun), the preposition goes in between the parts.

Examples:

- Hech kimda savol yo'q.

- *No one has any questions.*

- U hech narsa bilan keldi.

- *He came with nothing.*

Conclusion

It should be noted that a rhyme is a group of words that have an abstract meaning and an independent function in the language, and partially indicate the objects and their symbols, as well as the syntactic connections between the objects. Although pronouns are used in place of different word groups, they do not directly express the subject and their meaning.

Therefore, instead of concluding, the negative pronouns in English and Uzbek differ structurally in their use in speech, but there is almost no change in meaning in translation.

Above, we have only considered the specifics of negative pronouns. If we analyze other rhymes in the same way, it becomes clear that they have their own stylistic, semantic features, the scope of their use, their versatility and differ from other word groups.

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